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EXTRACTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF MUCILAGES FROM FRUITS OF *CORDIA LATIFOLIA* AND *AEGLE MARMELOS* FOR ITS MUCOADHESIVE BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT

Mucilages are generally normal products of metabolism formed within the cell and may represent storage material, a water storage reservoir or protection for germinating seeds. Literature review reveals that different sources of natural mucilages have been studied and being used as pharmaceutical excipients. The present research work aimed at extraction and characterization of *Cordia latifolia* (Cordia) and *Aegle marmelos* (Bael) fruit mucilages for various physico-chemical properties and investigation of mucoadhesive ability of extracted mucilages. The mucilages were successfully extracted from the fruits of Cordia and Bael by aqueous extraction using acetone (1:3) as precipitating solvent; percent yield were found to be 19%w/w and 14%w/w respectively. The extracted mucilages were characterized for solubility, swelling index, pH, loss on drying, melting point microbial load, micromeritic properties, rheology, FT-IR and mucoadhesion. From results it was found that the extracted mucilages were polysaccharide, hydrophilic, nontoxic and thermostable. Results of swelling study concluded that, cordia mucilage has good swelling behaviour in comparison to bael mucilage hence incorporation of these materials into tablet formulations would control release profile and mucoadhesiveness. The mucoadhesive nature cordia and bael mucilage was studied by physical methods. The Cordia mucilage is more mucoadhesive than HPMC whereas Bael mucilage is less mucoadhesive than Cordia mucilage and HPMC. Hence extracted Cordia mucilages can be used in formulation of various mucoadhesive dosage forms.

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INTRODUCTION

Mucilages are generally normal products of metabolism formed within the cell (intracellular formation) and may represent storage material, a water storage reservoir or protection for germinating seeds. Mucilage is formed in normal growth of plant by mucilage secreting gland. Being polysaccharide, they are partially soluble in water in which they swell and form gel. Mucilage is viscid somewhat tenacious and adhesive liquid prepared with water as solvent. Mucilage on hydrolysis yield a mixture of sugar and uronic acid. [1,2]

Mucilages are most commonly used as adjuvant in different pharmaceutical dosage forms such as tablets, suspension, gels, emulsion, syrup etc. They possess a variety of pharmaceutical excipient properties, which include binding, disintegrating, suspending, emulsifying, sustained drug release properties at different proportion in various pharmaceutical dosage forms.[3] Recent trends toward the use of the vegetable and non-toxic products demand the replacement of synthetic excipients with natural ones. Like other natural products, application of mucilage is increasing in industry due to non-toxic character, low cost, easy availability and appropriate quality. Now, it is necessary to explore the new sources of plant mucilages for industrial demand.[4]

Literature review reveals that different sources of natural mucilages have been studied and being used as pharmaceutical mucohesive excipient. The use of natural gum for pharmaceutical application is attractive because they are economical, readily available, non-toxic, and capable of chemical modification, potentially biodegradable and with few exceptions, also biocompatible. Many synthetic polymers such as carbopol 974, HPC and HPMC have been studied for their ability to sustain the release and mucoadhesion. However, still there is the need to identify the cheap, non toxic, natural and easily available materials for the mucoadhesion. Hence the present research work aimed at extraction of *Cordia latifolia* (Cordia) and *Aegle marmelos* (Bael) fruit mucilages and its characterization for physicochemical properties and mucoadhesion ability.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection of plant material:

Fruits of *Cordia latifolia* (Cordia) were collected in month of September to October and fruits of *Aegle marmelos* (Bael) were collected in the month of March to May from the Satpura regions of Jalgaon district, Maharashtra, India and authenticated by Department of Botany, RTM, Nagpur University, Nagpur.

Extraction and Isolation of Mucilage:

Cordia mucilage:

The collected fruits were washed thoroughly with water to remove adhering material. Accurately weighted 100g of *Cordia latifolia* fruits were taken and outer covering was removed. Pulp (100g) was macerated with 5 times of their weight of water and allowed to stand for 24h; then boiled for one hour with continuous stirring. The extract was then pressed through muslin cloth. The filtrate containing mucilage was used further for isolation of mucilage. The obtained filtrate was boiled at 70-80°C for 30 minutes, heating increases rate of mucilage extraction and inactivates enzymes. To the filtrate, acetone was added in 1:3 proportions to precipitate dissolved mucilage from glue. The so obtained precipitated mucilage was separated and dried at 50°C in hot air oven. The dried mucilage was powdered, passed through the BSS sieve No. 100 and stored in desiccator at room temperature till further use.[5]

Bael Mucilage:

The ripened fruit pulp of *Aegle marmelos* was separated and the seeds were removed. A known weight (100 g) of pulp was soaked in 2000 mL distilled water for 24 h, with occasional stirring. The soaked pulp was further ground in a grinder and kept for 24 h for the release of mucilage; then boiled for one hour with continuous stirring. The extract was then pressed through muslin cloth. The filtrate containing mucilage was used further for isolation of mucilage. The obtained filtrate was boiled at 70-80°C for 30 minutes, acetone was added to the filtrate in 1:3 proportions to precipitate dissolved mucilage from glue. The so obtained precipitated mucilage was separated and dried at 50°C in hot air oven. The dried mucilage was powdered, passed through the BSS sieve No. 100 and stored in desiccator at room temperature till further use. [6]

Percentage yield of Mucilages:

The percentage yield was calculated from the ratio of weight of obtained mucilage to the initial weight of fruit pulps. The percentage yields for extracted Cordia mucilage and Bael mucilages were 19% w/w and 14% w/w respectively.

Phytochemical characterization of extracted mucilages.

For identification of presence of phytoconstituents in extracted cordia and bael mucilages various chemical tests were performed as shown in Table No.1.[7-9]

Table No. 1: Phytochemical characterization of extracted mucilages.

Sr. No.	Phytoconstituents	Test	Observations	
			Cordia	Bael
1.	Carbohydrate	Molisch's test	+	+
2.	Mucilage	Ruthenium test	+	+
3.	Reducing Sugar	Fehling's test	+	+
4.	Starch	Iodine test	-	-
5.	Alkaloids	Wagner's Test	-	-
6.	Flavonoids	Shinoda Test	-	-
7.	Tannins	Ferric chloride test	-	-
8.	Steroids	Liebermann-Burchard Test	-	-
9.	Glycoside	Keller Killiani Test	-	-
10.	Protein and amino acid	Ninhydrin Test	-	-
11.	Chlorides	Silver-nitrate test	-	-
12.	Sulphates	Barium chloride test	-	-
13.	Uronic acid		+	+
14.	Foreign matter (%) (*NMT 0.1)		0.006%	0.004%
15.	Lead (heavy metal)		1.67 ppm	1.13 ppm
16.	Arsenic (heavy metal)		0.62 ppm	0.81 ppm

Solubility:

Solubility of mucilage was determined in different solvents such as cold water, warm water, ethanol, methanol, chloroform and ethyl acetate.

Swelling Index:

Accurately weighed 200 mg of previously pulverised mucilages were placed into a petri-dish and then 10 ml of distilled water was added and the mixture was shaken thoroughly every 10 min for 1 hr. It was allowed to stand for 3hr at room temperature. In between at an interval of every 1 hr the remaining water in petri-dish was discarded and the increase in weight of the mucilage material was noted. The weight increase is due to the sticky hydrogel nature of the plant material. The same procedure was repeated for three times and the mean value was calculated.[10,11] The swelling index was calculated for the cordia and bael mucilage in water, at pH 1.2 and 7.4. The result is given in Table No.2.

Observation:

$$\text{Where, SI} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1}$$

Where, SI = Swelling index, w1 = weight of mucilage before swelling, w2 = weight of mucilage after swelling

Loss on drying:**Procedure**

Accurately weighted one gram of each powdered drug samples were taken into flat and thin porcelain dishes. The dishes were dried in the oven at 105 °C and the weight was checked at intervals of 10min, until a constant weight was obtained.[10] The dishes were cooled in desiccator. The loss in weight of extracted mucilage was recorded and LOD was calculated by using given equation. The result is given in Table No.2.

$$\text{Loss on Drying} = \frac{(\text{Initial wt.} - \text{Final wt.}) \times 100}{\text{Initial wt.}}$$

Determination of pH of the mucilage:

The pH of 1% w/w solution of the cordia and bael mucilage was determined using a digital pH meter. Both mucilages showed pH 6.5±0.5.

Melting Point Determination:

The melting point of the mucilage sample was determined by melting point apparatus. The melting point of mucilage is recorded as shown in Table No.2.

Table No 2: Characterization of Cordia and Bael mucilage Powder.

Property of mucilage	Result	
	Cordia mucilage*	Bael mucilage*
Bulk density (g/cc)	0.415 ± 0.02	0.506 ± 0.03
Tapped density (g/cc)	0.564 ± 0.04	0.649 ± 0.02
Compressibility Index (%)	26.41 ± 0.37	22.03 ± 0.41
Housner Ratio	1.35 ± 0.08	1.28 ± 0.07
Angle of repose (°)	25°20' ± 0.46	22°40' ± 0.15
Swelling Index	15.21 ± 1.08	12.47 ± 0.82
Water Retention (%)	14.00 ± 1.29	12.00 ± 1.21
Loss on drying (%)	5.4 ± 0.18	4.8 ± 0.25
pH	6.32 ± 0.19	6.85 ± 0.23
Melting point (°C)	146 ⁰ - 150 ⁰	148 ⁰ - 151 ⁰
Practical yield (g/Kg)	160g-170g	135g-145g
Microbial Load (No. of CFU/gm of Mucilage)	4	3

*Each value represent the mean ± standard deviation (n=3)

Microbial Load:

The test is designed for the estimation of the number of viable aerobic micro-organisms present in extracted mucilage. Total viable aerobic microbial count was determine by plate count method. Casein soya bean digest agar such as medium 2 was added in each petri dish and allowed to solidify. Then pre treated sample preparation was spread on the solidified medium in a petri dish and it was incubate at 37°C for 72 hour. [12-14] Result was examined after 24 hour as shown in Table No. 2.

Particle Size Distribution:

Few particles of Cordia and Bael mucilage powder were taken on a glass slide, uniformly spread by a brush, such that individual particle can be seen and particle size distribution was measured by Microscope Image Analyzing System (Vision plus-5000).[15] The particle size distribution for both mucilage is given in Figure1.

Figure No 1: Particle size distribution of Cordia and Bael Mucilage.

Micromeritics of mucilage

In micromeritic characterization of extracted mucilage various parameters were studied such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped bulk, Carr's index and Hausner ratio were performed and the results are shown in Table No 2.

Rheology Study of Cordia mucilage and Bael mucilage:

Rheological measurements were carried out using a rotational viscometer (Brookfield R/S plus rheometer) equipped with C25 measuring spindles and for each test, approximately 0.2-0.5 ml sample was transferred to sample compartment (cone and plate). [16,17] Effect of concentration and varying pH on rheological behaviour of both mucilages was studied; results are shown in figure 2 and 3.

Figure No 2: Effect of Concentration on Viscosity of Cordia and Bael mucilage.

Figure No 3: Effect of pH on Viscosity of 1% a) Cordia and b) Bael Mucilage at Different Shear Rates.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR):

Extracted dried powder of cordia and bael mucilage was mixed thoroughly with potassium bromide. This physical mixture was compressed and converted in a circular disc. This disc was then placed in the scanning slot of FTIR and scanned to obtain the FTIR of cordia and bael mucilages as shown in figure no. 4 and 5.

Figure 4: FTIR Spectra of Cordia Mucilage.

Figure 5: FTIR Spectra of Bael Mucilage.

***In vitro* Mucoadhesion study of Mucilages:**

The mucoadhesive property of extracted mucilages(cordia and bael) were compared with commercial used synthetic polymeric material i.e. hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose(HPMC).

Shear stress measurement:

The shear stress measure the force that cause a mucoadhesive to polysaccharide with respect to the mucus layer in directional parallel to their place of contact of adhesion. Various concentrations of cordia mucilage, bael mucilage and HPMC such as 1%, 2% and 3% w/v aqueous solutions of isolated mucilages were prepared. Two smooth polished glass blocks of 10×10×0.5 cm were selected. One glass plate was fixed on a leveled table with an adhesive. To the upper block a thread was tied and passed through a pulley at a length of 12 cm. At the end of the thread a pan of 3 g weight was attached for the addition of weights. A drop of polysaccharide solution at a temperature of 25°C was kept at the center of the fixed block with a pipette, and the movable block was placed on it. A load of 100 g was applied such that the drop of polymer spread as a uniform film in between the two glass blocks. After keeping it for fixed time intervals of 5, 10, and 15 min, the applied load was removed and the weights were added into the pan just sufficient to pull the upper movable block or to make it slide down from the fixed base block. The sheer stress was expressed in gm/cm². [18]The result was compared with the result of the synthetic polymer as reported in literature.

Table No.3: Results of Shear stress measurement.

Name of biopolymer	Concentration (%w/w)	Weight required to detach glass plate(gms) at the time intervals		
		15 min	30 min	60 min
Cordia Mucilage	1	167.73 ± 2.37	186.33 ± 1.86	228.05 ± 1.76
	2	218.32 ± 3.69	235.78 ± 2.37	286.64 ± 2.11
	3	232.25 ± 2.86	265.10 ± 2.58	311.39 ± 2.95
Bael Mucilage	1	80.76 ± 2.45	121.47 ± 1.75	170.11 ± 1.57
	2	115.51 ± 3.31	158.86 ± 1.54	205.38 ± 1.93
	3	137.38 ± 1.56	192.19 ± 2.16	242.45 ± 2.89
HPMC	1	159.74 ± 1.76	181.37 ± 1.27	227.10 ± 2.42
	2	204.56 ± 3.38	219.94 ± 3.18	266.41 ± 3.08
	3	227.43 ± 3.14	236.48 ± 3.25	289.58 ± 3.17

*Each value represent the mean ± standard deviation (n=3)

Falling sphere method

A clean burette was taken and filled with 10% mucus solution and fixed in a stand. Mustard grain which retained on sieve size # 12 were taken and dipped in polysaccharide solution of concentrations (5 % w/v) and then each grain were slowly placed at the top of the mucus layer. Time taken by the grain to fall 50 divisions in the burette was noted and values were tabulated. [19,20]

Table No.4: Results of falling sphere method.

Name of biopolymer	Concentration (%w/w)	Average time taken (seconds)
Cordia Mucilage	1	14.34 ± 0.53
	2	15.27 ± 0.79
	3	17.42 ± 0.41
Bael Mucilage	1	9.57 ± 0.37
	2	10.29 ± 0.58
	3	10.88 ± 0.70
HPMC	1	12.44 ± 0.64
	2	13.82 ± 0.44
	3	14.49 ± 0.28

*Each value represent the mean ± standard deviation (n=3)

Wilhelmy's plate method:

The rectangular glass plate was coated with 1% w/v solution of extracted mucilages and dried at 60°C for 3 h. The glass plate coated with the extracted mucilages was allowed to immerse into the mucus solution kept in the beaker. The glass plate is attached to the weight tray, and the weight on the tray is adjusted so that the glass plate stays stationary. The glass plate is allowed to remain in the mucous solution for the specified intervals. [19]

During the contact of the glass plate with the mucous solution for a specified time the extracted mucilages forms a binding force with the mucous solution. After the specified time interval, the weight on the weight tray was gradually increased until the glass plate was pulled out of the solution. The weight in grams required to detach the glass plate was noted. The same procedure was repeated by using a freshly coated plate and varying the contact time of the glass plate in mucous solution. This experiment was conducted for cordia mucilage, bael mucilage and HPMC. The results are shown in Table No. 5.

Table No.5: Results of Wilhelmy's plate method.

Name of the biopolymer (1%w/v)	Weight required to detach(gm) At the time intervals			
	5min	10min	15min	30min
Cordia Mucilage	0.81	1.33	1.49	1.82
Bael Mucilage	0.63	0.87	1.06	1.39
HPMC	0.76	1.21	1.38	1.76

DISCUSSION

Bioadhesion can be defined as the process by which a natural or a synthetic polymer can adhere to a biological substrate. When the biological substrate is a mucosal layer then the phenomena is known as "mucoadhesion". The natural mucoadhesive material can be used for retardation of the drug release. They have been used in tablets, suspensions or as a matrix system for sustaining the drug release. Various natural material and polymers are being used as agent for sustained release of different drugs. These substances, when comes in contact with water, get hydrated and gel form. The drug release from this gel will be usually diffusion controlled and hence the release will be sustained over a prolonged time. Many hydrocolloids such as guar gum, xanthan gum, karaya gum and mucilages from *Cassia tora*, *Ocimum canum*, *Ledidium sativum*, *Asparagus racemosus*, *Aloe vera*, *Althea rosea* and *Althea officinalis* have been reported to sustain the drug release from matrix tablets.

Extraction and Separation of Mucilage:

Extraction method was set on trial and error basis. As mucilages are soluble in hot water hence natural mucilage material from natural sources viz; *Cordia latifolia* and *Aegle marmelos* were extracted by cold and hot aqueous extraction process followed by the organic solvent precipitation.

During extraction fruits cordia and baels were kept for 3 hours in hot water to complete transfer of mucilages from fruit pulp to hot water. To carry out precipitation of solubilised mucilage from water, various precipitating solvents such as ethanol, chloroform and acetone were tried. Amongst these solvents acetone gave highest yield and white colored precipitate, hence acetone was finalized as a precipitating solvent. The extracted material from the cordia and bael fruits are collected and yield was found to be high in the fruits of cordia 19% w/w and low in the fruits of bael 14% w/w.

Evaluation of Mucilages:

Phytochemical characterization of extracted mucilages.

The purity of mucilage was determined by prescribed phytochemical tests, which indicated the absence of alkaloids, glycosides, steroids, flavanoids, saponins, tannins, chloride and sulphate. The mucilages gave positive test for uronic acid which is general constituent of mucilage. Only carbohydrates were found to be present, which confirms the purity of mucilage. The amount of foreign matter was found negligible. Extracted mucilages were also analyzed for levels of toxic heavy metals(Lead and Arsenic) and found to be within acceptable limits as specified by WHO.[10]

Solubility Test:

The solubility of the cordia and bael mucilage has been studying by using different solvents. It was found that both extracted powders showed swelling in cold water, solubility in warm water and practically insoluble in non polar solvents such as acetone, ethanol, chloroform etc. confirms presence of mucilage. The solubility in water is the prerequisite for any mucoadhesive agent. Since, the extracted materials are hydrophilic they are suitable as a binding agent and mucoadhesive agent in pharmaceutical formulations.

Swelling Index:

The results of swelling index study revealed that the mucilage material absorbs more than ten times of water by its weight. From obtained results of swelling study it can be concluded that, cordia mucilage has good swelling behaviour as that of bael mucilage. Hence incorporation of these materials into tablet formulations would enhance the better release profile and mucoadhesiveness. The swelling index of the dried mucilages was performed using different solvents such as distilled water, pH 1.2 acid buffer and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. The swelling index of cordia and bael mucilage were found to be 15.21 ± 1.08 , 12.47 ± 0.82 in distilled water, 14.05 ± 1.19 , 10.36 ± 0.64 , in acid buffer pH 1.2, and 12.59 ± 0.73 , 11.29 ± 1.31 in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 respectively hence it can be concluded that swelling of both mucilage was pH independent. The swelling index of cordial and bael mucilage was almost comparable to that of HPMC; hence the said mucilage ensures the suitability to use for mucoadhesive drug delivery system.

Loss on Drying:

Both extracted powder showed significant amount of moisture in it i. e. 5.4 ± 0.18 and 4.8 ± 0.25 therefore it was stored in the desiccator.

pH of Mucilage:

The pH of 1% w/v solution of cordia and bael mucilage was 6.5. Both the materials were found to be slightly acidic. Hence, the tablet formulations that can be made from these materials would be compatible and would not irritate the mucous membrane of the GIT.

Melting point:

The melting points of the extracted mucilages of cordia and bael were found be $146-150^\circ\text{C}$ and $148-151^\circ\text{C}$ respectively. The high range of melting point indicates that the materials are thermo stable within the operational range of temperatures at which the different pharmaceutical dosage forms were formulated.

Microbial Load:

The microbial load test was performed to check total microbial count and presence or absence of pathogenic microbes. The study showed that the total bacterial and fungal count was within the limit i. e. less than 4 cfu/g for bacteria and 3 cfu/g for fungi as prescribed by Indian Pharmacopoeia on the isolated and purified natural mucilages.

Particle size distribution:

Particle size determination is important as it is affecting various micromeritic properties such as bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Housner's ratio, Carr's index etc. Hence particle size distribution and average particle size of extracted mucilages was determined and found to be within narrow size.

Micromeritics of mucilage

In micromeritic characterization of extracted mucilage various parameters were studied such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped bulk, Carr's index and Hausner ratio were performed and the results are shown in Table No.2. From results it can be stated that the extracted mucilage has satisfactory flow ability as well as tableting characteristics.

Rheological Measurement:

The rheological measurement of the Cordia mucilage and Bael mucilage sample at different concentrations and pH was performed which showed that by increasing the concentration of mucilage, its viscosity increases. Also increase in the viscosity of mucilage solution was found when pH was increased supported by Kooheki et al.[16] These finding can be explained as induction of the electrostatic repulsion by functional group that tends to keep the molecules in an extended form, thus producing a high viscous solution. Also due to presence of uronic acid, carboxyl group are ionized so much that viscosity reached maximum. This effect was upto pH 8. After pH 8, the viscosity of solution was constant. Results are as shown in Figure 2-3.

FTIR Study:

The FTIR spectra of both the mucilages gave almost similar except that sharp peak was observed for cordia mucilage at 1050 cm^{-1} . Further FTIR spectra of both the mucilages showed the absorption at wave number $3500 - 3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the OH stretching. The broad band in this region showed that the OH is hydrogen bonded. The absorption at 2950 cm^{-1} was due to the C-H stretching in the molecule. The absorption at $1750 - 1715\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was due to the presence of C=O bond which may be due to presence of aldehyde of sugars and carboxyl group of uronic acid. The absorption at 2800 cm^{-1} may be because of the C-H stretching of aldehyde. The absorption at $1130-1023\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to C-O, C-C stretching of glycosidic bond. FTIR study revealed the characteristic groups for a carbohydrate molecule.

***In vitro* Mucoadhesion study:**

The study was carried out by different methods such as shear stress method, wilhelmy's method, and falling sphere method. The mucoadhesiveness of sample is due to the interaction between the mucin, a glycoprotein present in the mucosa of the intestine and the drug polymer matrix. Generally hydrophilic groups such as $-OH$, $-COOH$ and $-NH_2$ are attributable to such interactions. The mucoadhesive nature cordia and bael mucilage was studied by physical methods. The mucoadhesive property of the extracted cordia and bael mucilage material was compared with HPMC.

Shear stress method:

From results it can be stated that, with increase in concentration of polymeric solution shear stress (weight required to detach glass plate) also increases for extracted mucilages and HPMC. Amongst the biopolymers under study bael mucilage exhibited lowest mucoadhesion whereas cordia mucilage exhibited highest and comparable mucoadhesion to HPMC.

Further it also has been observed that, as the holding time increases shear stress also increases. This indicates that maximum force in grams is required to break the bond between the polysaccharide and the mucosal surface with increase in holding time. It was observed that increasing the contact time for adhesion and mucoadhesion increased the force required in terms of weights for of all the natural materials. Therefore, increasing the time of contact increased the adhesion and mucoadhesion strength, allowing for greater adhesion and mucoadhesion. The cordia mucilage exhibited excellent bioadhesive strength. Further increment in the biomaterial concentration did not affect its bioadhesiveness. The shear stress study revealed that higher concentration of biopolymeric solutions showed promising mucoadhesivity comparable to standard HPMC.

Falling sphere method:

In-vitro mucoadhesive property of the extracted mucilage was evaluated by falling sphere method. The results of falling sphere method are as shown in Table No.4. From results it can be observed as concentration of the biopolymeric solution increased, resistance to move of the mustard towards bottom side was also increased. Time in seconds required to move the mustard grain from top to bottom in 3 % w/v solution of Cordia mucilage, bael mucilage and HPMC $17.42 \pm$ were found to be 17.42 ± 0.41 , 10.88 ± 0.70 and 14.49 ± 0.28 seconds respectively. This indicates that higher the concentration of the polysaccharide increases the adhesiveness of the polysaccharide containing mustard and decreases the downward movement.

Wilhelmy plate method:

The *in vitro* mucoadhesivity of the extracted mucilages and HPMC was studied by Wilhelmy Plate method which showed that the cordia mucilage possesses a promising mucoadhesivity in comparison to HPMC and bael mucilage. The results are as shown in Table No.5. From the results it was observed that among the extracted mucilage, cordia mucilage exhibited highest mucoadhesion and bael mucilage exhibited lowest mucoadhesion property. The process of mucoadhesion has been proposed to begin with the establishment of an intimate contact between the mucoadhesive polymer and mucus gel. The possible mechanism of its mucoadhesive property may be the interaction of mucus with carboxyl or hydroxyl groups of the biopolymers.

CONCLUSION

The mucilages were successfully extracted from the fruits of Cordia and Bael by aqueous extraction using acetone (1:3) as precipitating solvent. The extracted mucilages were characterized for various physicochemical properties from results it was found that the extracted mucilages were polysaccharide, hydrophilic, nontoxic and thermostable. It has been showed that the Cordia mucilage is more mucoadhesive than HPMC whereas Bael mucilage is less mucoadhesive than Cordia mucilage and HPMC. Hence Cordia mucilage may have high potential for substitution for other more expensive synthetic mucoadhesive polymers.

Authors' Statements:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Abbreviations

HPMC - Hydroxypropylmethylcellulose,
HPC - Hydroxypropylcellulose,
ppm - parts per million,
CFU - Colony forming unit,
LOD - loss on drying,
FTIR - Fourier transform infrared,
WHO - World Health Organization.

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